

Biocarbon based Polymers for Sustainable Material Development

Deliverable D6.1

Website, Twitter and LinkedIn accounts live

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Executive Summary

This document, *D6.2 Website, Twitter and LinkedIn accounts live* is a deliverable of the **D-Carbonize** Project, which is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101073223. The document describes the motivation behind the concept of the website and the objectives as a key tool for dissemination and communication actions. The document provides a description of the public site, defining also the social media tools used, such as Twitter and LinkedIn.

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1. Purpose of the Website, Twitter and LinkedIn account live Deliverable

The Website, Twitter and LinkedIn account live is one of the deliverables of the WP6: *Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication*.

The main purpose of this deliverable is to describe the key points of design, execution, content usage and communication strategy behind the internet platform of the **D-Carbonize** project. The URL of the website is <https://dcarbonizeproject.eu/> and it has been online since the beginning of March 2023. The Twitter and LinkedIn accounts of the project were created at the same time. Additionally, an Instagram account was also created. Both the website and social media networks constitute key communication tools to increase the projects visibility and impact towards the different audiences identified in the proposal: Research and educational community, Industry, Policy and decision makers, General public. They are also important tools for sharing information between the D-Carbonize partners and Doctoral Candidates (DC). The website includes a private intranet to be used by the partners handling confidential information.

2. Main Objectives and Responsibilities

The website directly contributes to the main objectives of the WP6, since it is a key dissemination and communication tool. It is the main source of information of D-Carbonize for all audience targets, including project members. The website will act as a data collector and document sharing between all the project members and also it will inform and reach out the general public showing them the relevance, pertinence and importance of the transition towards a circular economy and more specifically the need for developing biobased plastics that can be recycled. Social media will complement all this information and will help reach a wider audience.

ICIQ is the responsible for the development, updates and maintenance of the website and social media, as leader of *Task 6.1 Design and publication of the D-Carbonize website and social network*, in close collaboration with the WP6 leader, AIMPLAS, ensuring a high degree of coordination between all the tasks within the WP. All consortium members are responsible for regularly contributing to the contents of the website and are engaged to support the **D-Carbonize** website by disseminating it through their own websites and social media channels. DCs will be involved too in updating the web with their results and the activities carried out.

3. Website Development and Description

D-Carbonize website is accessible at: <https://dcarbonizeproject.eu/>. The platform has been created to serve as a key tool to support external communication and dissemination of the project objectives and results. It is also used to centralize DC applications process through the intranet, a private area used only by the partners, where to handle confidential information.

The website displays the following main sections:

- **Home:** landing page that includes a brief description of the project. Besides, the homepage shows the main highlights: the latest events and news, consortium information, access to the other web sections, information on EU funding and access to the project social media.
- **Project:** information about the project's vision, including access to the sections: summary, research, training, outreach and outputs.
- **Network:** summary of the participants in the project and access to beneficiaries, doctoral candidates and associated partners pages.
- **DC Positions:** information about the open positions, job conditions, eligibility criteria and required documents. It also includes the application link.
- **Events:** a list of the events related with the project, including a brief explanation of each one.

- **News:** includes three sections: news related with job opportunities, news about the activities developed in the project and the newsletter subscribing form.
- **E-Learning:** portal where tutorials, handbooks and software applications will be included.
- **Intranet:** private intranet to handle confidential information between the partners. Used in the selection process.
- **Contact:** information about the project main contacts.

3.1 Home

The Home page is designed to attract the attention of viewers by exposing the project logo and banner, listing the content of the website. It presents the project at a glance, highlighted news and events and consortium partners (figure 1). It also includes reference to Horizon Europe and European Commission (EC) support.

All sections of the website have on top the **D-Carbonize** logo and the menu bar enabling quick orientation through the search. At the bottom, all sections provide links to project's social network.

E-Learning Intranet Contact

HOME PROJECT NETWORK DC POSITIONS EVENTS NEWS APPLY HERE

NETWORK / DCS

Twelve Doctoral Candidates will be integrated in a multidisciplinary & interdisciplinary team formed by 6 academic groups, 5 companies and 1 industry association all focused on a common goal. The 12 DCs will be awarded double doctoral degrees by 2 universities in 2 different countries at the end of the training program.

RESEARCH & TRAINING

D-Carbonize brings together leading high-education institutions, research centers and companies to form an innovation community able to offer excellent research and training both in R&D and entrepreneurship.

EVENTS

D-carbonize will host several network-wide training events to provide our DCs with the necessary skills to succeed in their scientific career as well as with tailored soft skills: 3 Workshops (open to external DCs) and 1 D-Carbonize School will be organized throughout the project lifetime.

Events

Kick-off Meeting

D-CARBONIZE School

E-Learning Intranet Contact

HOME PROJECT NETWORK DC POSITIONS EVENTS NEWS APPLY HERE

News

Extended the deadline to apply to positions until April 16

Mar 30, 2023

You still have time to apply for one of our 12 positions and become part of the D-Carbonize network. The deadline to apply for positions has been extended to April 16. Remember that we are looking for 12 Doctoral Candidates who want to become future leaders in the...

Published our positions for Doctoral Candidates. Apply now!

Mar 6, 2023

You can now check out all our Doctoral positions to join the D-CARBONIZE network aiming at using circular chemistry approaches to design and build recyclable bioplastics using biomass. We are looking for 12 Doctoral Candidates who want to become future leaders in the...

D-CARBONIZE project: a new era for sustainable polymers

Feb 20, 2023

The project D-CARBONIZE is a joint doctorate network that aims at using circular chemistry approaches to design and build recyclable bioplastics using biomass as a starting material. Global excessive disposal of plastic waste is creating serious problems leading to...

[SEE ALL NEWS](#)

Figure 1. Home page

3.2 Project

Project page (figure 2) includes access to five different sections:

- **Summary:** brief description of the project (figure 3)
- **Research:** includes scientific objectives and research work packages (figure 4)
- **Training:** explains the primary training goals. Besides, includes the local training and information about workshops and D-Carbonize School (figure 4)
- **Outreach:** it will contain information about the outreach activities carry out in the project
- **Outputs:** this page will serve to make public the results of the project (e.g. peer-reviewed publications, public deliverables, etc.)

Figure 2. Project page

Figure 3. Summary page

Figure 4. Research and Training pages

3.3 Network

This section provides access to the beneficiaries and associated partners pages (figure 5). In both cases organizations logos are displayed and linked with their institutional websites (figure 6). It also includes the DN Candidates page with a link where they can apply to the open positions. Once the 12 DN candidates have been selected, the DN candidates page will show relevant information (picture, position, short biography, etc.) about each of them.

Figure 5. Network page

Figure 6. Beneficiaries and Associated partners pages

3.4 DC Positions

This section displays the 12 DC available positions (figure 7). Clicking on each position icon, a pdf file opens with a description of the individual project, institutions involved, candidate profile, eligibility criteria, employment conditions and procedure to apply (required documents).

The screenshot displays the 'DC Positions' page on the D-CARBONIZE website. The page features a grid of 12 position cards, each representing a different DC project. Each card includes the following information:

- DC Title:** A brief description of the project's focus.
- Main host institution:** The primary organization leading the project.
- Secondary host institutions:** Other organizations involved in the project.
- Duration:** All positions are listed as 3-month roles.

At the bottom of the grid, there is a green button labeled 'APPLY HERE'. Below the grid, there is a section for 'Job conditions' which states: 'Appointment under full-time employment contract for a period of 36 months'.

Figure 7. DC Positions page

3.5 Events

The events section will include a list of all the events related with the project (figure 8), including (initially) a brief explanation of each one of them and later on (after the event has taken place) the main highlights. At present, there is some initial information about the planned project Workshops, the D-Carbonize School and the Kick-off Meeting section.

Figure 8. Events page

3.6 News

The News page is divided in three different parts. The Job/Vacancies section include information about the open positions and in the future, it might include information on job offers/vacancies of interest for the members of the network. The Activities section provides information about the news, events, highlights and any other relevant topic related with the project and the network. In the Newsletter section there is a form, for individuals interested in the projects, to subscribe to the D-Carbonize bi-annual newsletter. Twice a year the Newsletter will be published on the D-Carbonize website.

Figure 9. News page. Activities section.

Figure 10. News page. Newsletter section.

3.7 E-Learning

This (open access) section will include tutorials, handbooks and software applications related with the project and the associated scientific knowledge, interesting and useful for the scientific community and the general public.

Figure 11. E-Learning page

3.8 Intranet

The website includes a private intranet to be used by the partners handling confidential information. It is also used for the DC candidate's selection process, to centralize all the applications received and evaluate them.

3.9 Contact

Details of the main project contacts are included in this section (figure 12). The e-mails of the Scientific Coordinator, Prof. Arjan Kleij, and the Project Manager, Dr. Anna Banet, are available together with the **D-Carbonize** general contact e-mail: info@dcarbonizeproject.eu

Figure 12. Contact page

4. Social Media channels

Social media accounts are key to increase awareness of the project, disseminate the project's outcomes, communicate the news and events, and interact with the different stakeholders and the general public. The main social media channels used are: Twitter ([@carbonize_d](https://twitter.com/@carbonize_d)), LinkedIn ([/d-carbonize-227136268/](https://www.linkedin.com/company/d-carbonize-227136268/)) and Instagram ([@d_carbonize](https://www.instagram.com/@d_carbonize)).

4.1. Twitter

It serves to boost the project's visibility among the general audience, researchers, companies and partners, massively, and interact with them. ([@carbonize_d](https://twitter.com/carbonize_d))

Figure 13. D-Carbonize Twitter profile

4.2 LinkedIn

It serves to promote the initiative among a specialized community. It emphasizes **D-Carbonize** news and events, as well as other relevant items. ([/d-carbonize-227136268/](https://d-carbonize-227136268/))

About

The project D-CARBONIZE is a joint doctorate network that aims at using circular chemistry approaches to design and build recyclable bioplastics using biomass as a starting material.

Global excessive disposal of plastic waste is creating serious problems leading to microplastics accumulating in our ecosystems and plastic patches growing in the oceans. To overcome these adverse side-effects, we need a paradigm shift from a linear to a circular polymer production and (re)use. The D-CARBONIZE project aims to close this existing gap transitioning to a circular use of renewable-carbon

Figure 14. D-Carbonize LinkedIn profile

4.3 Instagram

It serves to promote the initiative's actions; it will be especially important to show pictures and videos of the project experiments. ([@d_carbonize](https://www.instagram.com/d_carbonize))

Figure 15. D-Carbonize Instagram profile